

CULTiVATE

BARCELONA CITY PROFILE

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BARCELONA CITY PROFILE

Geography and Economy

Barcelona is located in a strategic geographical point along the Mediterranean coast in north-eastern Spain. Barcelona is the capital city of Catalonia autonomous community and the city is located between the Collserola ridge and the sea, and bordered by a river delta in each side, the Besós and Llobregat rivers. The Serra de Collserola Mountain range, which covers 8,000 hectares at the border of the city, acts as a “green lung” for the metropolitan area. The city has four kilometres of beaches and one of the most important ports of the Mediterranean¹. Barcelona is a centre of commerce, tourism, art, architecture, sports, science and culture. It is visited annually by 8.3 million tourists². Barcelona is ranked 16th in the 2021 Economist/Intelligence Unit’s Global Liveability Index, and 4th in the 2023 European Best Cities Report conducted by Resonance Consulting³. Barcelona aspires to be a champion of the solidarity economy, with over 2,400 third sector organizations, 197 worker-owned enterprises, 861 cooperatives and 260 community-economic initiatives as reported in 2016⁴. In 2022, Barcelona registered the lowest unemployment rates in 15 years, consolidating employment in dynamic strategic sectors such as ICT, tourism, commerce and creative sectors⁵. The average annual income per person in the province of Barcelona is the fifth highest in Spain, however, in 2020 almost 22% of the population were at risk of relative poverty, and 36% of households struggled to make ends meet⁶. Barcelona is home to tech multinationals and global firms that establish their European digital hubs in Barcelona, as well as over 2,000 tech start-ups. The Boston Consulting Group states that Barcelona is the 5th most attractive city in the world for digital experts⁷. Barcelona’s citizens are highly connected to the internet with 92% of households having internet connections, and 85% having a computer. The digital divide between citizens of the city has narrowed in recent years, with only a small percentage of households not having an internet connection, with most of these being homes of people over the age of 74^{8,9}. Barcelona has become a centre for research and innovation in different areas, with special focus on social innovation to reduce inequalities and improve its residents’ wellbeing¹⁰.

Politics and Society

The Kingdom of Spain is a constitutional monarchy with a democratic parliament ruled by King Felipe VI. The government is divided into legislative, executive, and judicial powers with elections held every four years. Barcelona is the capital city of the autonomous community of Catalonia, which has its own parliament and executive council with extensive autonomy. The Catalan region represents around 16% of Spain’s total population¹¹. Catalonia has its own national identity, language, and culture, and an independence movement that has gained strength in recent decades¹². With a population of 1.64 million, it is Spain’s second largest city and one of Europe’s most densely populated^{13 14}. The city council is organized in two levels: the political structure, which defines the city strategy; and the executive council, which develops concrete actions to achieve the goals. The political council is elected every four years. Since 2015 progressive parties with strong social and environmental agendas have been governing the city. The metropolitan area of Barcelona consists of 36 municipalities, and the city itself is divided in 10 districts which comprise 73 neighbourhoods^{15 16}. This offers decentralised management where neighbourhood projects are developed in coordination with district offices that are in close contact with citizens and civil society organizations¹⁷. The municipality has an agency to promote social and solidarity economies with the goal of transforming the city to become more democratic, sustainable, collaborative and equitable, with focus on citizens and their wellbeing¹⁸. Barcelona has a high level of cultural diversity with 24% of its residents born abroad. Immigration has been a key driver for the city’s recent economic

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and population growth¹⁹. Barcelona's non-national residents come from South America (24%), Asia and Oceania (23%), the European Union (23%), Africa (11%), North and Central America (11%), and non-EU European countries (9%)²⁰.

Food and Food Culture

Barcelona is surrounded by agricultural land which provides 16% of locally produced food. In 2016, 8,6% of households experienced some form of food insecurity in the city, reaching over 23% in the most vulnerable districts, where there is more poverty and lower presence of organic products^{21 22}. However, Catalan culture has a rich history of diverse food economies including food cooperatives, collectives, alternative food initiatives and food commons. In 2018 there were 57 agroecological cooperatives which provided food for 1,420 families. As a result, initiatives to increase food safety, reduce food waste, feed vulnerable communities, or other social and neighbourhood initiatives under agroecological and social solidarity economy criteria are happening all around the city^{23 24}. In 2021 Barcelona was the capital of Sustainable Food, which led to the development and publication of the “Strategy for Healthy and Sustainable Food” in 2022. This strategy seeks to transform the city's food system to become more transparent, resilient, participative, safe and equitable, based on principles of agroecology and aimed at tackling the climate emergency²⁵. Food is a central part of Spanish and Catalan culture, with most social gatherings occurring around the kitchen and the table. The cultural and ethnic diversity of the city means cuisines from all over the world can be accessed in Barcelona. Alimentària Barcelona Food Fair, Terra I Gust, the Sustainable Food Festival, and the Soups of the World Festival are some of the many large gastronomic events that the city hosts, where thousands of people meet to share their passion for food together. Throughout the year, there are several seasonal gatherings centring around food in the city. In the winter, people gather to prepare and eat *calçots* (long sweet onions), that are cooked over the embers and accompanied by world-wide famous *romesco* sauce. *Paella* is the most popular dish during spring and summer. When autumn arrives, chestnuts and *panellets* are eaten in every corner of the city, and mushrooms can be found throughout the city's markets²⁶.

Environment and Sustainability

Barcelona's municipality has, since 2015, prioritised environmental and social justice. The city council seeks to ensure quality public spaces, develop a green and biodiverse city that is both productive and resilient, and are committed to active and sustainable mobility. In 2020 the city declared a climate emergency, committing €563 million of investment and launching a plan detailing 100 specific measures to tackle it²⁷. Barcelona is a signatory of multiple global sustainability initiatives such as the United Nation's Global Compact Cities, the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, the C40 Cities, and the European SDG Index. Barcelona's “Nature Plan 2021-2030” details the vision and strategy for the city's development, which gives nature a central role. Its main goals are to increase the city's green infrastructure, maximise ecosystem services to increase urban biodiversity, and improve the quality of life for the city's inhabitants²⁸. This plan is accompanied by transition plans, and a new street transformation model (*superblocks*) creating a network of green hubs and squares²⁹.

BARCELONA FOOD SHARING LANDSCAPE

Quantity

Number of FSIs: **221**

Population per FSI (1.363.411 inhabitants.): **7493 inhabitants/FSI**

No. of translocal initiatives and online initiatives

Most initiatives in Barcelona operate only within the city. However, one multifunctional initiative, Espigoladors, operates across Catalunya and beyond, while other networks and online initiatives such as Pam a Pam also operate translocally.

In total, there are **20 FSIs without a physical location**, most of them focus on knowledge sharing, such as Pam a Pam, Ruralitzem, or BCN + Sostenible with Remena't being a website of the metropolitan area of Barcelona focused on food waste. These online initiatives were included in the database but are not visually represented on map.

No. of initiatives with multiple locations within the city and what they share.

13 initiatives have more than one location, most sharing food or knowledge/skills. If there were two locations, such as the Economat Social (a cooperative supermarket), present in Sants and Nou Barris, they were represented in both locations. If there were many locations, only the central address was used for the visual representation in the map.

Initiatives outside Barcelona's administrative boundaries

17 Initiatives mapped had locations outside of the city's administrative limits but part of the urban continuum adjacent to Barcelona and of the functional city are delimited by OECD. Extending the mapping method to include different locations such as Hospitalet de Llobregat, Sant Cugat del Vallès, Badalona, Sabadell, would have revealed more initiatives in the metropolitan area.

Sector of Sharing

FSIs were coded according to four sectors: collective growing, cooking and eating, redistributing and multifunctional, based on what their main activity was. The figures below were calculated by adding up all initiatives from each of the four categories. Then, the percentage out of the total number of initiatives was calculated. Some initiatives were deemed as multi-functional if more than one function (growing, cooking & eating, or redistributing) was conducted. Hence, the sum of all percentages is higher than 100%.

Table 1. Type of FSIs in Barcelona

Type of FSIs	No. of initiatives	% ¹ of total initiatives
Growing	86	38,91
Cooking	38	17,19
Eating	44	19,91
Cooking/Eating	62	28,05
Redistributing	79	35,75
Multifunctional	41	18,55
Total	221	100

Figure 1. Percentages of the type of FSIs

Barcelona's food sharing landscape is diverse and quite equally distributed across the different sectors of FSIs. Almost 39% of the initiatives focus on growing, while 35% on food redistribution, and 28% on cooking & eating. Almost 20% (41) of the initiatives focus on more than one sharing activity and are multifunctional food sharing initiatives (Figure 1).

Growing initiatives consist mainly of urban gardens, many of which are owned by the municipality and managed by entities with a social focus (such as elderly people or mental health). Others are community gardens from social centres or associations. There are also growing initiatives dedicated to knowledge & skill sharing about urban agriculture.

Food redistribution initiatives have also different profiles. The most common are consumer cooperatives, which are groups of neighbours that organize the weekly provision of local agroecological food directly from the producers. There are also a few cooperative supermarkets. Another kind of re-distribution initiatives are those that recover surplus food from different channels.

Cooking & eating initiatives are often cooperative or social & solidary economy restaurants, which provide jobs and help vulnerable collectives through gastronomy. There are a few community kitchens and shared culinary hubs.

¹ NB: Figures add up to more than 100% because some initiatives engage in multiple activities and are considered multifunctional initiatives.

Figure 3. Key words of the mission statement/goals of Barcelona's FSIs

Figures 2 and 3 show how FSIs emphasised the social goals of their activities. Terms such as social, community, space, or cooperative appear often. Environmental terms, such as consumption, garden, local, ecological, appear regularly albeit less frequently than social ones.

What is shared

Data on 'what is shared' was collected based on the activities of FSIs and further compiled in three broad categories: stuff, skills, and spaces. We analysed the resultant data in two ways, first by the full range of elements being shared and then by broader categories of material stuff (Food; Meals; Plants; Seeds; Tools; Compost), skills (knowledge and skills) and spaces (land and kitchen). To establish what is shared by FSIs in Barcelona the occurrence of each term in the three broad categories was counted and summed up. The percentage of FSIs sharing an element was calculated by dividing the sum of each term by the number of initiatives. For example, if the code 'food' occurs 50 times, this would be divided by the total number of FSIs identified in a city. FSIs can share more than one thing which means that the sum of percentages per category of things being shared will be greater than 100%.

FSIs in Barcelona share a wealth of things, some with a physical composition like seeds, plants, meals and gardening tools or kitchen devices, while others are focused on sharing knowledge and skills or sites and spaces. When the activities of 221 FSIs identified in Barcelona were categorized by categories based on what they were sharing (knowledge, skills, meals, food, etc.), food was the most shared "element" followed by knowledge, skills, and land (Table 4, Figure 4). Note, FSIs often share multiple elements, for example sharing food and skills related to growing, cooking and preparing it, hence the sum of all % is higher than 100.

Table 2 What is shared

Clusters of what is shared	No. of FSI	% of total FSI	Terms	No. of FSI	% of total FSI
Knowledge & Skills	124	56,1%	Knowledge	119	53,85
			Skills	83	37,56
Stuff	189	85,5	Food	148	66,97
			Meal	47	21,27
			Plants	25	11,31
			Compost	29	13,12
			Seeds	10	4,52
			Tool	5	2,26
			Kitchen Device	12	5,43
			Spaces	74	33,5
Land	61	27,60			

Figure 4. What is Shared by elements (% of FSIs)

Over 85% of the initiatives shared material elements, including food, meals, compost and plants. More than half shared skills and knowledge, and more than a third of the FSIs shared spaces, mostly community gardens sharing land (Table 2, Figure 4). As many of the FSIs mapped in Barcelona have multiple goals, it is unsurprising that more than half of the initiatives share more than one thing (Table 3). Many FSIs accompany their main activity with an educational side, sharing knowledge and skills on top of food or meals, for example. This shows how the food sharing movement in Barcelona is composed by holistic multi-goal and multifunctional projects, tackling many environmental and social issues simultaneously.

Table 3 FSIs that share more than one element

Multiple sharing	No. of FSI	% of total FSI
Initiatives that share more than one thing	131	59,3
Initiatives that share 3 or more things	89	40,3

Modes of sharing

FSIs in Barcelona adopt a range of different ways to share (termed modes) from bartering and gifting to selling and collecting (Table 4, Figure 5). Bartering involves exchange of goods or services, gifting implies no monetary exchange, whilst selling can be not-for profit or for-profit. Collecting refers to activities such as gleaning or foraging. Data on approaches to sharing was taken from FSI profiles and allocated to one of these modes. Note, FSIs may use more than one mode of sharing across their activities. Data on FSIs mode of sharing was counted using the occurrence of representative codes, percentages were further calculated by dividing the occurrence of terms by the total number of initiatives. As certain initiatives use more than one mode of sharing, the resulting statistics do not add up to 100%.

Table 4. Modes of sharing

Mode of sharing	No. of FSI	% of total FSI
Collect	11	4,98
Gift	129	58,37
Barter	25	11,31
Sell	112	50,68
Multifunctional	55	24,89

Figure 5. Bar chart of Barcelona's FSIs modes of sharing

Gifting is the most common sharing mode for Barcelona's FSIs. This is likely due to the social drivers behind many of the FSIs, which are often dedicated to supporting vulnerable sections of the population who may have limited financial resources. While selling is the second most common method, this is predominantly due to the prevalence of cooperatives and social economy restaurants, many of which are not-for-profit (see section on organisational structure of FSIs). These initiatives suggest alternative ways of consumption, reducing environmental or economic costs of food, or adding a societal value to the consumption of food, but still involve monetary interactions. Bartering and collecting were less common, and often combined with other modes of sharing. This is not uncommon in FSIs as bartering requires complex negotiations about what constitutes a fair exchange, while collecting relies on the existence of wild harvests or legal frameworks around who can legitimately collect food from where (e.g. in relation to gleaning or skip surfing activities).

Social and Environmental Focuses

Identification of the motivations and goals of FSIs, enabled analysis of the particular focus of initiatives. These were allocated to three/two categories: social, economic and environmental. Social goals were identified as those related to supporting specific groups of populations, such as migrant, ethnic, disabled, gendered or other communities which can suffer food insecurity. Activities which focused on education social justice, health & wellbeing or community development were also included within the social scope. Initiatives allocated to environmental focus were those which goals included mainly sustainability, food waste reduction and biodiversity. Initiatives which focused on job creation or insertion, and economic promotion were categorised as Economic.

Table 5. Categorization of FSI's goals

Goals/Focus	No. of FSI	% of total FSI
Social	142	64,3
Economic	27	12,2
Environmental	164	74,2
More than one	117	52,9

Figure 6 Bar chart of the categorization of FSI's mission/goals

Almost 75% of the initiatives had environmental goals and most were related to some form of sustainability, either producing locally sourced food, reducing food waste, provisioning ecologically produced food, etc. Almost 65% of the FSI were related to a social goal. The majority of these focused on community development, creating neighbourhood networks that increased social cohesion. Some others were aimed at helping vulnerable cohorts. Fewer initiatives had an economic goal, aimed at activating local economies or generating jobs. More than half of the initiatives had multiple goals (Table 5, Figure 6).

Organisational structure of initiatives

While the definition and legal categorisation of organisational structures is not uniform across Europe such organisational analysis is still useful to delineate splits between for-profit and not-for-profit across locations. The organisational categories are based on, but also extend, those established in the SHARECITY project³⁰. The identification and calculation of percentages of FSIs organizational mode followed the same procedure as for the other coding categories. The occurrence of an organizational term was counted and divided by the total number of FSIs. As FSIs can operate under more than one organizational framework the percentages do not add up to 100%. For example, an initiative can be registered as a non-profit, but can run a social enterprise to finance the non-profit activities

Table 6. Organizational structure of FSIs

Sharing organization	No. of FSI	% of total FSI
Charity	0	0,00
Non-profit Organisation	44	19,91
Social Enterprise	3	1,36
For-profit Organisation	16	7,24
Cooperative	63	28,51
Club	0	0,00
Association	60	27,15
Network	0	0,00
Informal Organisation	7	3,17
Public Sector	31	14,03

Figure 7. Bar Chart of Barcelona's FSIs Sharing Organizational structure

FSIs in Barcelona adopt a range of organisational structures to operationalise their activities.

Table 6 and Figure 7 show that more than a quarter (28%) of FSIs were organized as a cooperative, and an association (26%). This is related to the supports for solidarity economy initiatives in Barcelona and the strong social movements in the city that have the capacity to enact them. Almost 20% of the FSIs were non-profits, indicating a strong social motivation for food sharing which often focuses on vulnerable sections of the city population who may be at risk of food poverty. Despite the supports from Barcelona municipality for the solidarity economy, only around 14% of FSIs identified were categorized as public sector-led. However, the public sector also plays a key role in many other FSIs by providing access to spaces or financial resources. Compared to the high levels of multifunctionality amongst FSIs and multi-modal nature of sharing already demonstrated in this report, only 3 initiatives operate more than one organisation type in Barcelona.

Technology

In order to be mapped the FSIs had to have a digital profile in the form of a website (or web application), Facebook, Twitter/X, Instagram or Meetup. Exploring these profiles enables exploration of the means of communication used by FSIs to publicise their activities. Once identified FSIs were cross checked with the remaining social media platforms and via Google search engine to see if they had a presence or a website. FSIs often have a presence on more than one platform or have both a website and social media profiles.

Table 7. Forms of ICT used by Barcelona's FSIs

ICT used	No. of FSI	% of total FSI
Website	207	93,67
Meetup	2	0,90
Facebook	118	53,39
Twitter	88	39,82
Instagram	104	47,06

Figure 8. Bar chart of forms of ICT used by Barcelona's FSIs.

Most FSIs had their own website, only 14 FSIs did not have their own website. Facebook and Instagram were the most used social media platforms, while Meetup was barely used (Table 7, Figure 8).

SPATIAL ANALYSIS

The previous section provided an overview of the composition of FSIs within Barcelona. This section focuses on the location of FSIs. This spatial analysis is conducted only with FSIs that have a physical location within Barcelona or its peri-urban area (as noted earlier there are four initiatives without a physical location in the municipality). There are also 13 cases where an FSI has multiple locations in the city. In these cases, the central address of the organization was represented in the map. There were also 20 FSIs operating outside the administrative boundary of Barcelona but within the commuting area delimited by the OECD. These are included in the following maps. A range of spatial analyses follow, including: concentration of FSIs across Barcelona (and concentration by FSI sector); clustering of FSIs, and analysis of the location of FSIs relative to: population density, foreign populations, age, education, income and employment.

All the analysis is made at the district level. Barcelona is divided in 10 districts, each of which contains several neighbourhoods. Figure 9 shows the city's districts coded by numbers, which will be used during the following discussions.

Figure 9. Overview of Barcelona's districts

Concentration Analysis

To work on homogeneous areas, the territory of Barcelona was divided in a hexagonal tile grid of 500m of radius. The analysis considers this grid as it refers to the “15-minute city” concept. Indeed, citizens have an average walking speed of 2 km/h on their daily routes to reach public services, green areas, public transport stops, supermarkets, and other basic services. The number of FSIs existing in each tile were

calculated and then categorised according to the sector of sharing (growing, cooking & eating, redistributing).

Figure 10 below provides an overview of the concentration of FSIs across Barcelona. This map was created by calculating the sum of FSI present in each hexagon of the generated grid. Then, the map was colour coded to see in darker red the most concentrated areas of the map.

Figure 10. FSI Concentration Map

This map reveals the concentration of FSIs in the city, where darker red means higher FSI concentration. Central districts of the city exhibit higher FSI concentration, with the lowest concentration in the north-western districts.

Concentration Analysis: Growing

Figure 11. Concentration of FSIs which grow food in Barcelona by district

Figure 11 shows that the growing initiatives are relatively well distributed across the city, albeit having a relatively stronger presence in the northern districts of the city, along the Collserola mountain, where there is higher space availability for urban agriculture. In Vallcarca, a northern neighbourhood of the Gràcia district (06) there's an area with high concentration of growing FSIs, having 2 gardens dedicated to elderly people, a self-managed neighbourhood community garden, and an activist initiative that helps recover unused urban spaces for urban agriculture. This is due to the higher space availability in the district, plus the historically known alive social movements that activate such initiatives.

Concentration Analysis: Redistribution

Figure 12. Concentration of FSIs which redistribute food in Barcelona by district

Figure 12 shows how redistributing FSIs are present in all districts of Barcelona. There are, however, a number of hot spots of redistribution activity. In Gràcia (District 06), there is a community neighbourhood centre which hosts 4 cooperative consumer's groups, and in Sants (District 03) there is Can Batlló, a neighbourhood centre which hosts many community activities, such as a cooperative consumer's group, a dumpster-diving group or a cooperative supermarket.

Concentration Analysis: Cooking and Eating

Figure 13. Concentration of FSIs which cook and/or eat food in Milan by district

Figure 13 shows how cooking and eating initiatives are more concentrated in the southern districts of the city, where there is higher population density and therefore likely to be more demand for social initiatives to provide support to vulnerable sections of society. There are some initiatives outside the city borders, in the municipalities adjacent to the city, which can be observed in the map. In the south-west of the map, in el Prat de Llobregat, a hexagon where 2 FSIs can be observed. It is es-imperfect, a social enterprise by Fundació Espigoladors (CULTIVATE partner) dedicated to cooking gleaned food into repurposed products. Also, Menja, Actua, Impacta (Eat, Act, Impact) is nearby, an exposition with workshops around eating and sustainable food systems.

FSIs Clusterisation

The categorisation of the sectors of sharing allows for developing a three-scale chropleth map, which shows the diversification level of the food sharing landscape in Barcelona. By blending colours (multiply), the map reveals the presence of sectorial and multi-sectorial clusters of sharing across the city.

Figure 14. Clusterisation by sector of FSIs

The cluster map (Figure 14) reveals the areas with more food sharing activity in the city, seeing more density and diversity of initiatives in the central districts (Ciutat Vella – 01, L’Eixample -02, and Gràcia - 06) and Sants - Montjuic (03), as hotspots of cooking/eating & redistributing initiatives, while more growing FSIs concentrate in the northern districts (Gràcia - 06, Horta – Guinardó - 07).

Demographic, Social and Economic Indicators

The concentration analysis set out above provides a clear picture of the locational aspects of FSIs, however geography alone cannot explain why FSIs locate in particular places. The following analysis explores whether there may be correlations between location of FSIs and other socio-economic variables, including the location of FSIs relative to: number of inhabitants per FSIs, population density foreign populations, ageing index, education level, average individual gross income, and unemployment rate. The analysis here is also done at the district level due to data availability.

Inhabitants per FSI

Figure 15 shows the number of inhabitants per FSI in each district, to get a normalized measure of the concentration of FSIs in the city.

Figure 15. Map of FSI distribution and residents per FSI

Figure 15 supports the conclusions of the Cluster map by sectors (Figure 14), which indicated that Gràcia, Ciutat Vella, Sants-Montjuic, followed by l'Eixample are the districts with most FSI activity.

Population density

Previous research has demonstrated that dense populations provide the network effects needed to support ICT-mediated sharing. With this in mind, population density per municipality was layered over the location of FSIs.

Figure 16. Map of FSI distribution and population density by district

In Figure 16 we can see the distribution of FSI and the population density of the city (inhabitants/km²). The central districts of the city (Ciutat Vella, Eixample, and Gràcia) are the most densely populated. The eastern districts (Sant Martí, Sant Andreu and Nou Barris) follow, connected with the urban continuum of the municipalities along the Besòs river. Horta-Guinardó and Les Corts follow in density, located at the periphery of the city but well connected to the more densely populated districts. Sarrià - Sant Gervasi and Sants – Montjuic are the least densely populated districts, coinciding with the presence of larger green areas in their territories. However, Sants – Montjuic is highly concentrated in its urbanized area, which might be misleading in the analysis below. FSI concentration seems higher where population density is higher.

Figure 17. Scatter plots of number of FSIs and population density by district. Top plot including all districts. Bottom plot excluding district 03 (Sants – Montjuïc), outlier due to the presence of a large natural area which reduces population density value.

Figure 17 shows a positive correlation between population density and FSI concentration. The outlier in the graph is Sants-Montjuïc, a district containing a large natural area which decreases the population density. Moreover, this district is known for having a large culture of cooperatives and social movements, reflected in the amount of FSIs identified.

Foreign Population

Given the focus of many FSIs on supporting vulnerable or marginalised sections of society to integrate into communities, the concentration of foreign populations within municipalities was compared to the locational incidence of FSIs.

Figure 18. Map of FSI distribution and foreign population

Figure 18 shows the percentage of foreign population per district, having Ciutat Vella distinguished as the most diverse districts of the city, where 52% of the residents are foreign. This Figure also indicates that richest neighbourhoods are the ones with fewer foreign residents, which also correlates with lower FSI concentration.

The outlier is Ciutat Vella, the old town in Barcelona, which has twice as more foreign residents as the other districts. If we remove this outlier and repeat the graph, we see that there is a correlation between the migrant population and the FSI concentration (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Scatter plot of Number of FSI and Foreign Population. With all districts (left), without outlier Ciutat Vella (right)

Population density was then plotted against foreign population. Both Ciutat Vella and Sants-Montjuic were removed from the plot since they are outliers. Ciutat Vella has a much greater percentage of foreign population, and Sants Montjuic has a much lower population density due to the presence of a large natural area in its territory. There appears to be a correlation between both variables, which could indicate that foreign population is not an explanatory variable itself since it is determined by population density. However, the data sample is too small to state that these correlations are significant.

Figure 20. Scatter plot of Foreign Population and Population Density. With all districts (left), without outliers Ciutat Vella and Sants Montjuic (right)

FSI distribution and non-EU Foreign Residents

An additional analysis was performed to see if there were differences in composition of foreign population along districts, checking the percentage of non-EU foreign population, as shown in Figure 21.

Ciutat Vella has 38% of non-EU foreign citizens, out of the 52% foreign population. Nou Barris has 19% non-EU out of the 21% total foreign residents. Only in the richer neighbourhoods have higher EU residents, and in the rest the non-EU percentage is much higher.

Figure 21. Map of FSI distribution and Non-EU foreign population

Ageing Index

The aging index is the ratio between population older than 65 to population younger than 15. It was used in this context to explore the location of FSIs relative to this index which is shown below, Figure 22.

Figure 22. Map of FSI distribution and aging index

We can observe how the whole city presents high values for this index meaning that Barcelona has a relatively old population, with L'Eixample and Les Corts having the oldest relative districts, and Ciutat Vella as the youngest. Figure 23 below indicates that there is no correlation between the FSI concentration and the aging index.

Figure 23. Scatter plot of number of FSI and aging index

Education level

The location of FSIs was considered in relation to educational attainment levels by district and shown in Figure 24 below. The education level is shown on the legend as the percentage of residents above 15 years old with higher education, understood as having a bachelor's degree or more.

Figure 24. Map of FSI Distribution and % of residents with High Education

Looking at the education level of the population above 15 years old, we see differences among the city's districts. Nou Barris has the lowest percentage of residents with higher education (less than 20%), while Les Corts, Sarrià Sant Gervasi, Gràcia and L'Eixample have more than twice that percentage. However, no correlation was found between these differences in aging index and the concentration of FSIs per district, as shown in Figure 25. This lack of correlation means that age is not a determining factor in the distribution of FSIs across the city.

Figure 25. Scatter plot Number of FSI and Residents with High Education.

Individual Average Gross Income

As many FSIs focus on supporting sections of society considered vulnerable or marginalised, often due to low income, the individual annual average gross income was compared to the local incidence of FSIs, as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26. Map of FSI distribution and Average Gross Individual Annual income

Examining income per district, Ciutat Vella and Nou Barris have the lowest annual income per capita, with less than €15,000, while Sarrià – Sant Gervasi reaches over €33.000. The districts with more residents with higher education coincide with the higher annual income.

The richest districts (Sarrià Sant Gervasi and Les Corts) seem to have less FSI concentration. Interestingly, the two following richest districts, located more centrally (Gràcia and Eixample) have higher FSI concentrations than poorer districts. This could be explained by greater availability of resources (financial and otherwise) to support FSI activities in these areas.

Figure 27. Scatter plot Number of FSI and Income.

Income does not seem to be a variable that explains the distribution of FSIs along the city, since the level of correlation is very low, as shown in Figure 27.

Unemployment

Figure 28 shows the % of the population between the ages of 15-65 years who are not in work nor training.

Figure 28. Map of FSI distribution and unemployment

The unemployment rate map aligns with the income map, showing the poorest districts have higher unemployment rates and the richest districts have lower rates. However, when comparing FSI concentration with unemployment rate there does not appear to be a strong correlation, as shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Scatter plot Number of FSI and Unemployment rate (%)

CONCLUSION

This report documents the form, focus and location of FSIs across Barcelona and reveals a rich and diverse picture of the food sharing activities that operate within the municipality and its peri-urban area. Compared to similar mapping of Barcelona conducted in 2016³¹ the number of FSIs has more than doubled which indicates strong expansion of activities over the past decade.

While mapping is essential for locating practices within the city, it is also a necessary step for establishing any unevenness in distribution by different sectors of FSIs across the city. Various socio-economic variables were compared with the incidence of FSIs to explore whether any correlations emerged. No strong correlations were identified, although the limited availability of granular data and the low number of FSI data points restricts the level of statistical analysis that can be undertaken.

Further in-depth exploration of the drivers behind the establishment (or not) of particular FSIs in specific locations will be further explored through the CULTIVATE project running until December 2026.

¹ <https://www.meet.barcelona/en/visit-and-love-it/location>

² Garcia, X., Garcia-Sierra, M., & Domene, E. (2020). Spatial inequality and its relationship with local food environments: The case of Barcelona. *Applied Geography*, 115, 102140.

³ <https://www.barcelonaglobal.org/know-how/barcelona-in-the-rankings/>

⁴ <https://use.metropolis.org/case-studies/growing-a-social-and-solidarity-economy-to-regenerate-neighborhoods>

⁵ <https://www.barcelona.cat/internationalwelcome/en/news/barcelona-closed-2022-with-several-economic-records-1261157>

⁶ https://www.barcelona.cat/infobarcelona/en/tema/city-council/what-are-people-like-in-barcelona-and-how-do-they-live_1164847.html

⁷ <https://catalonia.com/why-catalonia/tech-and-digital-hubs>

⁸ https://www.barcelona.cat/infobarcelona/en/tema/city-council/what-are-people-like-in-barcelona-and-how-do-they-live_1164847.html

⁹ Ajuntament de Barcelona, BIT Habitat, 2020. The Digital Divide in the City of Barcelona.

¹⁰ <https://www.meet.barcelona/ca/estudia-i-investiga/barcelona-es-innovacio>

¹¹ <https://www.idescat.cat/indicadors/?id=aec&n=15332>

¹² <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-europe-20345071>

¹³ <http://www.amb.cat/en/web/area-metropolitana/coneixer-l-area-metropolitana/poblacio>

¹⁴ <https://www.idescat.cat/emex/?id=080193>

¹⁵ <https://www.amb.cat/s/web/area-metropolitana/municipis-metropolitans.html>

¹⁶ <https://www.barcelona.cat/ca/viure-a-bcn/fem-barri>

¹⁷ <https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/ca/organitzacio-municipal>

¹⁸ <https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/economia-social-solidaria/ca/impulsem-less-piess/qui-som>

¹⁹ Garcia, X., Garcia-Sierra, M., & Domene, E. (2020). Spatial inequality and its relationship with local food environments: The case of Barcelona. *Applied Geography*, 115, 102140.

²⁰ <http://www.amb.cat/en/web/area-metropolitana/coneixer-l-area-metropolitana/poblacio>

²¹ Bartoll, X.; Pérez, K.; Pasarín, M.; Rodríguez-Sanz, M; Borrell, C.. Resultats de l'enquesta de salut de Barcelona 2016/17. Barcelona: Agència de Salut Pública de Barcelona. 2018. Disponible a: https://www.aspb.cat/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/ASPB_Enquesta-Salut-Barcelona-2016.pdf

²² García, X., García., Domene. E. (2021) Entorns alimentaris locals a Barcelona. Actualització i anàlisi comparativa 2016-2019. Informe Executiu. Novembre 2023. Gerència d'Economia, Recursos i Promoció Econòmica. Ajuntament

de Barcelona. <https://www.institutmetropoli.cat/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Entorns-Alimentaris-Locals-IERMB-RESUM-EXECUTIU.pdf>

²³ Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2021. Urban agriculture Observatory

²⁴ Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2021. How does Barcelona feed itself? Executive Summary

²⁵ Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2022. Barcelona healthy and Sustainable Food Strategy for 2030. Executive Summary

²⁶ Agència Catalana de Turisme, 2014. Catalonia is Gastronomy. https://act.gencat.cat/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/03_Gastronomia_ANG.pdf

²⁷ <https://www.barcelona.cat/emergenciaclimatica/en>

²⁸ Area of Urban Ecology, Barcelona City Council, September 2021. Nature Plan 2021 – 2030

²⁹ <https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/superilles/en/>

³⁰ Davies, A. R., Edwards, F., Marovelli, B., Morrow, O., Rut, M., & Weymes, M. (2017). Making visible: Interrogating the performance of food sharing across 100 urban areas. *Geoforum*, 86, 136-149

³¹ Davies, A. R., Edwards, F., Marovelli, B., Morrow, O., Rut, M., & Weymes, M. (2017). Making visible: Interrogating the performance of food sharing across 100 urban areas. *Geoforum*, 86, 136-149